

Concerning Sustainable Protection of Family and Business

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Home Security	3
Financial Security	3
Cybersecurity	5
Disaster Preparation	6
Family Mobilization	9
Militia or Para-militia Organization	10
Sustainable Communities	12
DO:	12
Regarding "How to Get Started":	13
Ammo, Armor, and Arms	15
Arms	15
Let's talk about firearms	16
Let's talk about Mil-grade weapons	17
Let's talk about non-firearms	18
Let's talk about Home Defense	19
Survival Information	21
Let's talk about learning Survivalism	22
Clothing and Apparel related Survival	23
Canning and Food Prep, etc.	23

Home Security

The prime concern, as the age of political violence and riots commences in the west, as a result of competing forces of democracy, terrorism, demographics change, globalism, anarchism and socialism collide, is of course home and family security.

Checklist:

- Alarm, preferably smart alarm (not Google Nest)
- Cameras and door/window sensors
- Motion sensors
- Smart CO & flooding sensors
- Floodlights
- Glass security-film, made by 3M
- Firearms, ammo, all appropriate cleaning materials etc.
- Compartments
- Plenty of lanterns, flashlights, batteries and rechargeables
- Fuel generator or higher calibre generator
- Radio for emergencies
- Backup communications (walkie talkies, etc.)
- Optionals:
 - Front door bar/jam
 - Variably placed weapons, including pepper sprays tasers etc.
 - Dogs
 - Privacy fencing and even more advanced fencing
 - Shatter sensors
 - True fireproof vault, perhaps a gun safe
- Consider displaying security signage outside to dissuade robbery.

The main goal in home security is to create an emergency recovery system or backup buffer, and the second is to pre-dissuade would-be attackers. The issue of would-be attackers is that they typically pre-select victims based upon assumptions of ease of predation, or of escape. Typically a desire to escape is even more important, but if one is in the habit of *enticing* predators, such as with dark places, or repetition habits, or leaving open windows, or doors unlocked, this can be an issue.

Take for example, the fact that children can sometimes leave open garage doors, or they simply don't shut. A smart app on the phone with connection to garage sensors can be checked nightly, along with setting the alarm before bed.

As for the survival related items on the checklist, it is more important to think about the long term survivability of the home in times of local, regional, national, or global emergencies and catastrophes.

The decision for purchases will not be simple or straightforward (except the 3M security film, which is singular). But it must be decided to set aside a regular apportionment of the budget, monthly, yearly, or quarterly to make provision of purchases. In terms of priority that will depend on one's situation, and the neighborhood or countryside. But favor personal and anti-criminal security over long term survival with a 70/30 ratio.

Financial Security

One of a home's main security concerns is finance and budget "security." Most people think about their "retirement" which is to say they have a singular, and a bit nebulous goal. In reality very few people are able to save for retirement or plan for it. Those who have built businesses should work with my company, Resilient, to get the business ready for sale and have it prepared. Yet, getting it sold in time for retirement is not a guarantee, at all. So there are some things to consider.

Currently there is a strong likelihood of "financial reset" being discussed as coinage and even cash seem to be being "dried up" so to speak. This comes in juxtaposition to a rapid expansion of available capital and finance, and of course the juggernaut of financial derivatives market over \$1 Quadrillion in value.

The following cannot be construed as direct financial or securities advice. It is only an idea of a possible means of diversification and *hedge*.

1. For all businesses, open a brokerage account and set aside 10% (minimum) of profits
2. Also, do the same for all personal income and wages, at least monthly
3. Consider setting aside a certain amount of this to turn into pure cash
 - a. Optional: other currencies
 - b. Consider updating your passports as well.
4. Take another apportionment and purchase cryptocurrency, probably Bitcoin (BTC), probably through a Coinbase account until you are more familiar.
 - a. Purchase when Google Trend searches reveal low interest, and therefore lower prices.
 - b. Consult the cybersecurity guide for more information about cryptocurrencies.
5. Set up a gold/silver purchase account, and regularly track metals and make purchases as hedges against hyperinflation
 - a. DO NOT sell them at lower values than purchased. They do not expire, and are not stocks. Just hold them, indefinitely.
6. Consider purchasing ETFs or indices as hedges to portions of your account which are exposed to high risk mutual funds or stocks/options.
7. Consult a certified broker concerning your bonds and annuities, for long term planning.

Cybersecurity

First, download and use the Resilient approved [Cybersecurity for Small Businesses and Individuals](#) document. Consider, also, creating a Resiliency Plan or [Cybersecurity Checklist](#) for your company. This may involve working with [Resilient Firm, LLC](#), or you may consult your own experts and advisors, create an advisory board, etc.

Next, consider everything you do in terms of a digital footprint and “gap” that can be “exploited” via the Internet or electronics by digital terrorists or criminal enterprises, foreign or clandestine government operations, intelligence agencies, etc.

Consider your credit, finances, identity, and reputation as one single integrated health aspect. If you do, you will be better able to consider the ramifications of various behaviors, or decide on mitigating techniques (such as hiring a reputation management firm.)

The thing to remember is that World War 3.0 is a cold war, a digital war, and while China and Russia may be the principal actors, they are not the only threat. African and Eastern European hacker groups, as well as scammers, phishers, phreakers, etc. also will attempt to take and steal your identity. If you are an American citizen or European citizen (etc.) with a great track record, your identity is worth many thousands of dollars on the black markets, in the Deep/Dark Web to the right buyers. **Do not rely on the protection of the FBI or anti-virus software alone.** You'd be shocked to know how far behind these things are to the front line edge. In 2016 the CIA's hacking tool boxes were leaked to the Internet by wikileaks, and since then, the use of sophisticated anti-IT protection software has bloomed and increased exponentially. It is almost assured that your identity will be/has been compromised and may be stolen or used for nefarious purposes, especially over the next 20-30 years. Credit Check Total is a service offered by Experian for free because of the high prevalence of identity theft, a service that use to cost \$30+ per month. We highly recommend setting up an account and locking your credit profile. When you want to apply for a new line of credit, you simply log-in and unlock your account in seconds. Discover card users also have access to Transunion reports with their accounts. In general Experian offers free Deep Web ID theft scanning.

The other thing to consider is the rising threat of AI, deep fakes, and other security compromising algorithms which could fool you, fake authorities, confuse people, creating completely false news, or encircle your positions in order to control you, your voting habits, your thoughts, your investing and financing habits, and political beliefs. This is *already happening, and it is not a science fiction conjecture but de facto status of the Internet TODAY.*

Disaster Preparation

There are too many types of disasters to prepare individually for, and a brief resiliency or survival plan should be considered to be developed for your individual case for each of the possible situations:

- Asteroids/meteors
- UFO raid
- Hurricanes/Typhoons
- Tornadoes
- Earthquakes
- Tsunamis/Megatsunamis
- Fire
- Riot / civil unrest
- Civil war
- Invasion
- Flash or mass flood
- Volcanic explosions and pyroclastic flows
- Plague (especially ebola)
- Drought and severe famine
- Government tyranny
- Economic crash/reset
- Magnetic Pole Flip and crustal collapse, etc.
- Nuclear holocaust
- Other WMD situations

This is not an exhaustive list. For most of these, though, it boils down to “hunker & bunker” or “flee the scene.” The answer to this will depend on your preparation, supplies, individual capabilities, willingness to act or resist, the scale of the disaster, the instincts which drive you, and the laws of survival.

Let’s use an example: the landslide collapse of Las Palmas island which could create a 1,000 foot or more megatsunami which would reach the east US coast within 8 hours. The immediate question is: what is your elevation and risk? Do you have a route to higher ground? In 2011 the Japanese Fukushima tsunami exposed the willful ignorance of coastal cities which had warning stones from past ages, and built below. Their retaining walls were incapable of holding it back, and many died... in winter. It was a national disaster and an international catastrophe as the nuclear power plant was damaged and has continued to dump material into the ocean.

So what is your disaster preparedness (on a scale of 1 to 10) for each of the above, with 10 being perfect preparation (such as a well established and completed survival checklist as found in FM21-76¹, or similar. Write your answers above, and be frank.

Secondly, make a survival checklist inventory, such as follows, and we have left room for budget considerations so you may easily establish a basic plan to be a remediation for many disasters, such as earthquakes and tornadoes, or riots.

¹ <http://www.equipped.com/fm21-76.htm>

Item	Stock	Storage	Acquisition considerations	Budget
Flashlights				
AA batteries				
D batteries				
12V batteries				
AAA or C batteries				
Lanterns				
Coleman type stove				
Flint and fire materials				
First aid and survival kits				
Compact fishing kit				
Radio for emergencies				
Walky Talkies or ham radio				
Blankets and EMR foil				
Fire extinguishers				
Bolt cutters				
Pry bar or claw hammer				
Hand saws				
Shovel, pick axe etc.				
Backup generators and fuel				
Non firearm weaponry (bows, etc.)				
Snakebite or speciality kits				
Thermite/Explosives capabilities				
Electrical & safety equip.				
Candles				
Dry wicks				
Spare fuses				
Survival knives				

Pliers, etc.				
Wire ² or string				
Climbing or other durable rope				
Tactical vests				
Armor + carriers				
Pepper spray				
Gas masks				
Goggles				
Swimming kit				
Tasers or stun guns				
Spare coats				
Cover-alls and long-johns ³				
Balaklava or ski mask				
Any type of training equipment ⁴				
Maps, Compass, & Protractor				
Spare parts (guns, cars, etc.) list....				

Note - list firearms and ammunition, etc. on a separate list.

Remember the above is a guidepost, and the goal is for you to create a comprehensive list and 1 page plan for different situations. Consider it like your family fire escape plan, but for scarier situations even than house fire. When things happen you have to be ready to move. Again consider a house fire. Some years ago my wife's grandfather accidentally started a fire in the middle of the night, and they barely escaped with a guitar and a photo or two. Other than that the fire was complete devastation. Even the fireproof safe failed and the

² Not just for electricity, but can be combined with cans and bottles to create a tripline warning system around an encampment.

³ Most people are focused on global warming but actually Earth is due to enter a rapid cooling phase at any moment.

⁴ See Militia section

firearms were destroyed. Relatively speaking a house fire is a grade 1 catastrophe. So prepare for the grade 4+ situations and it may actually ameliorate such a situation. Hope for the best, prepare for the worst.

Family Mobilization

In an emergency situation, it will be difficult to rely on cell phones. In 2010 in San Diego we experienced a 4.8 or so sized earthquake. There was no damage, anywhere. Still the cell phone system was blocked for almost 45 minutes. In 2011 San Diego had dual transformer stations blow up due to A/C overusage (heat wave). People suspected terrorism at first. The power was out mid day for 5+ hours, but more importantly the cell phone system was completely worthless for 8+ hours. If you have small children, or elderly (or others you have to do caretaking for), pets, horses, rare or vulnerable property, etc. you may be left on your own without EMS or police services for extended (or indefinite) periods of time. In Lexington, KY in the early 2000's a single ice storm eliminated electricity for thousands for up to 2 months. This is a serious threat to life and limb. Make contingencies, including planning for mobilization - or traffic gridlock - during disasters. Consider alternate routes, and options. What are your family's limitations? What are the chokepoints of the family? Are you an "easy mark" for grifters, criminals, and other predators during such situations? People in desperate times are like drowning persons: they will take you down even if it wouldn't help them, merely out of panic.

Several years ago a man drowned trying to save another man stuck in a deceptively slow moving gyre of water. It looked harmless and weak as far as currents go. It was a very slow moving whirlpool. Yet both men drowned. People are routinely caught off guard by sudden tidal shifts and rogue waves, forest fires or backdraft situations, etc. How much more to consider when there is a widespread panic like a tsunami or Katrina/ASro Dome type situation? Do not fail to mitigate for such situations for your family, on account of cost or time it would take to consider the consequences, and have a few disciplined family meetings!

1. Make escape routes
2. Plan for canning food and MRE supplies
3. Exchange ammunition stock and consider shoring up on deficiencies
4. Test each other in skills (such as bow drill or other firestarting, making of shelters, etc)
5. Go on expeditions or train together.
6. Review training materials and "Cross pollinate" plans.
7. Review with children emergency info (present in terms of heart attacks, strokes, or home invaders to avoid frightening them too much).
8. Update materials on a regular schedule, at least once yearly.

Militia or Para-militia Organization

This document is not meant to replace the best guide of a trustworthy source, General Westmoreland's document PM8-94⁵. Instead it is (again) a general resource.

A militia should *not* be a political or terroristic organization, nor try to take the place of official police activities. Organizations such as NFAC, and to a lesser degree the Proud Boys, must be discouraged if they exceed "peaceful" gathering status. Instead, a militia is a 4th line of defense for citizenry.

1. Military
2. National Guard
3. Police and EMS
4. State Militias
5. Local group militias

If the situation has devolved to the last two, then the situation would be dire, as it will constitute the least well trained, and generally out of prime (physically speaking) individuals. Citizens are soft, and they are mostly passive.

Still, it may be possible to organize individuals for mutual defense of the USA and Constitution, (The People), and defend neighborhoods from rioting and attacks as were seen in Portland, Kenosha, and Seattle in spring to summer of 2020, subsequent of the Coronavirus lockdown. When the NFAC and Black Lives Matter communist organizations invade dLouisville, KY, Proud Boys peaceably assembled to ensure businesses were not destroyed, and working in conjunction with the police, the widespread destruction seen in Kenosha and Portland was completely avoided. This was due to first the preplanning phase and second, willingness of a non-local militia to work with the local government to comply with state laws. There were some shootings, where NFAC members accidentally shot their own members, illustrating again the problem of training with citizen militias in issues such as firearms safety. It is **never acceptable** for a militia member to endanger the citizenry through unlawful or negligent use of firearms.

Contradictorily, it is illegal to train local militias in para military intentions, without registering the group or getting permissions for the governor. Therefore, Gen. Westmoreland makes the wise suggestion that an individual recruit and organize small, (not massive political groups) militias around the idea of "paintball" or "airsoft" training. One may find both sympathetic citizenry, work on military skills, and have a generally safe environment.

It is important to consider, however, the unfortunate misunderstanding of the FBI (now controlled by the Deep State, and possibly under sway of the United Nations' Agenda 2030 "Great Reset" plans), to label such groups as paramilitary or "homegrown terrorist" organizations. Also the media has a penchant for labeling all groups as "white supremacists" and of course ignoring groups such as the Black Hebrew Israelites, NFAC, BLM, antifa, etc. Therefore, it is recommended that one consider security paramount:

- Do not use Facebook or Twitter to organize
- Use secure email only, not major email outlets (consider protonmail)
- Use secure communications apps such as Signal
- Do **not** do illegal things like encrypt ham radio communications, instead use "secure" electronics equipment.⁶
- Only admit people whom you personally know and can vouch for their character, intention, and law-abiding behaviors.
- Have members take the oath to the Constitution and the United States (or your own country, if foreign)
- Hold people at a distance to top training, and only invite them to the airsoft or paintball, until they prove their intentions and loyalty.

⁵ https://constitution.org/1-Activism/mil/doc/How_to_Start_&_Train_a_Militia_Unit--PM_8--94.pdf

⁶ <https://youtu.be/olyckKhZrpA>

- Value loyalty over talent.
- Look for determined, well-trained individuals to take up leadership in the organization.
- Be careful admitting National Guard members, as a man cannot serve two masters, and they may consider it a duty to report on your activities to their officers, who may or may not approve/understand the purpose of the organization.
- Same with cops, firemen, etc. depending on proclivities.
- Avoid religious, racial, and exclusive political biases in formation and recruiting decisions.
- Do not collect money together unless you form a trust or nonprofit - **stay inside the law**.

It is important to remember that homegrown terrorism, jihadism, drug cartels, mafias/la cosa nostra, racial supremacy groups, gangs, and religious cults constitute an active, and **dangerous** threat to the US Constitution, and citizenry. Therefore, take the training seriously while having fun. Be sure to keep the organization tightly run, but do nothing serious which could be construed as a paramilitary or military police type operation. It is definitely illegal, and is not protected by the 2nd amendment, to countermand local or regional/state government authorities. However, in rare cases, patriotism and defense of nation and family, etc. dictates this may be necessary. "Enemies foreign and domestic" is a realistic phrase throughout history. But do bear in mind the old adage, "loose lips sink ships."

Sustainable Communities

As similar to the militia organization issue, this is a multifaceted issue, and there is no easy guide here. The subjects regarding Sustainable communities involve:

- Organization and Governance
- Religious or spiritual considerations
- Permaculture
- Aquaponics and hydroponics
- Hydrology considerations
- Fishery
- Canning and preservation
- Energy grid
- Medical
- Education
- Weather and emergency survival
- Security and Safety
- Growth planning
- Project and budget planning
- Miscellaneous

Miscellaneous might cover many more topics than can be considered here, and professional sustainable community experts should avoid critiquing this document on this fact alone. The fact of the matter is that whole volumes of planning and information regarding each of the subjects is necessary to make a community really work and thrive. There should be 10x as much planning as work time to produce, so as to avoid catastrophes as human as social division and drama, or as disastrous as government crackdowns and intrigue, (see: Wild Wild Country documentary).

The purpose of a sustainable or resilient community is to form a democratic, private community that is away from the System. If the System is able to exert control and influence, it undoubtedly will. This does **not** give an excuse for communities, of any kind (political, religious, militia, etc.) to avoid paying taxes or playing friendly with the government.

DO:

- Buy the land under contract or outright
 - Try to acquire the mineral rights
- Ensure you have water and future food supplies if you get “locked down”
- Pay your land taxes and income taxes
- Have some form of economy with the local community so as to have income to pay taxes
- Engage neighbors in a friendly, open way
- Explain your beliefs if asked, without presenting a threatening front
- Display openly security and trespassing signs, instead of relying on threats and ominous warnings
- Give off an air of pleasant control
- Avoid toxic demonstrations which seek to intimidate neighbors or make them feel it necessary to call the police, etc.
- Attend neighborhood or city council meetings and voice your group’s assertion of rights
- Appear sane when doing it
 - Remember: people have different beliefs than you, and probably do not understand why you want to feel separate from the System or Establishment

- ❑ NOTE: facts don't matter to people as much as how they feel (especially regarding trust) about the entire situation
- ❑ Prepare yourself and your generations for the likelihood of incursions
- ❑ Set up an educational system commensurate with your beliefs, which educates the grandchildren that they must educate the grandchildren.
- ❑ Plan for sustainability rather than for confrontation.
- ❑ Plan for confrontation as if you want to survive it and your children, too.

The government can, and has - even in America - punish and harm isolated and sustainable communities, as well as individuals who try to thwart the Establishment. Examples:

- Ruby Ridge
- Branch Davidian
- Oglala
- Nevada Ranchers (Bundy standoff)
- Duncan Lemb (shooting)
- Rajneeshpuram (Osho's puram in Oregon)
- Etc.

We take no stance on the meaning or legality of these crackdowns. But they are more common than reported, and many of them are instigated by government corruption. It is too late to defend yourself if you are already taken. If you have a positive structural and strategic Position, to begin with, you have a negotiating position. If you grow drugs or smuggle people in or out, or fail to pay taxes, you lose all that advantage, and no amount of decrying your Bill of Rights will work to protect what you have built. Respect the lion in the field: the US government!

Regarding "How to Get Started":

1. Begin putting together the planning documents above. An example of some governance think can be [found in this document](#).⁷
2. Look for land
3. Prepare conversion plans surrounding structures on your land or land you acquire
4. Raise funds
5. Gather transition materials
6. Look for cheap and easy opportunities - do NOT spend money excessively⁸
7. Advised: barter, and barter aggressively.
8. Look for cheap labor, people who want to escape the cruel world and be of use
9. Consider how important social considerations and beliefs are.
10. Plan for security from the very beginning.
11. Consider food, but do not over-consider it; natural foods are found just about everywhere, and game is typically plentiful if you know how to get it.
12. Get excited and inspired, and try to inspire your followers
13. Focus on the tribe that responds, not just friends or family, who more likely than not will not be as supportive as you wish/imagine.
14. Look into land trusts and governmental protections

⁷ Be aware that if you are offended by this document, you can of course build governance around your religious views, etc. But no religious group has the right to use a form of law (eg. Sharia) which attempts to circumvent the Constitution of the United States of America (or etc. law wherever you are located).

⁸ I once saw a man buy a greenhouse of exotic plants in late November. Needless to say without the labor to put it all together, it was a waste of \$2600.

- a. Consider hiring an attorney for \$300/hr
- 15. Do not forget about bedding, clothing, shelter, fire, fuel, and foodstuffs + cutlery
- 16. Plan fairly assiduously, but be fluid and adaptable to changing circumstances
- 17. Review expert texts, such as the Mollison Permaculture⁹ text *beforehand*; but don't read 50 books!
- 18. Consider the Time, and of spiritual matters within yourself and around you; nothing flourishes without the Will of Heaven.
- 19. Be patient. "Rome wasn't built in a day."
- 20. Remember one thing about life, as accounted for in this very wise poem/song:

I close my eyes
Only for a moment and the moment's gone
All my dreams
Pass before my eyes with curiosity
Same old song
Just a drop of water in an endless sea
All we do
Crumbles to the ground, though we refuse to see
Now don't hang on
Nothin' last forever but the earth and sky
It slips away
And all your money won't another minute buy
Dust in the wind
All we are is dust in the wind

⁹ <https://archive.org/details/permaculture1adesignersmanualbybillmollison>

Ammo, Armor, and Arms

In considering your “AAA” insurance, there is a lot of information, personal considerations and opinions, and of course misinformation and unsolicited opinions. What follows makes the assumptions of a) novice status or b) forgetfulness. Think of it as a primer and reminder worksheet, not a “you must do this.” Besides that, you may ignore anything you don’t agree with. It is **your** insurance, after all.

Arms

- ❖ Type 1: blades
 - Knives
 - Swords
 - Axes
 - Battle axes
 - Maces
 - Halberds
 - Spears
 - Stars
 - Mechanical blades
 - Miscellaneous
- ❖ Type 2: firearms
 - Rifles
 - Shotguns
 - Handguns
 - Mil-grade rifles
 - Automatic vs. non-automatic
- ❖ Type 3: Military grade arms
 - Spec Ops grade
 - Technicals
 - RPGs
 - Machine guns
 - Mortars & artillery
- ❖ Type 4: Non-firearm arms
 - Bows
 - Crossbows
 - Atl-atl
 - Slings & slingshots
 - Airguns & spring loaded
- ❖ Type 5: Explosives
 - Molotov
 - Pipe bombs/bangalore
 - “Plastiques”
 - Mines & claymores
 - Black powder bombs
 - Military artillery grade (think battleship)

Bear in mind that going from Type 1 to 5 is a drastic decrease in importance for the sustainable community. In fact, it will surprise people that firearms are less important than blades, as a category. This is

because blades are multi-use, while firearms are only good for hunting, self-defense, and deterrence. Teaching your sustainable community how to wield spears and halberds, and hide knives on their person could be a matter of life and death later on. Unconvinced? Consider the following “Mad Max” scenario:

The US Government and world governments have fallen. Multiple warlords have set up power in the land, and small roaming bands of ronin-like gangs crop up. They look for easy marks, and for a good life. They hear by word of mouth that there is a land of plenty with good defensibility and plenty of women and food. They come in force, upon their hellish wheels, wielding overwhelming firepower that no rifles can repel. They come right in the middle of harvest and burn and slash. Can such an arrival, as it bursts through your opened, peaceful, unwatched or underwatched gates, be repelled? Is your community a paramilitary organization or an Amish-like religious community? More likely the latter. So now they take up residence. If there was a war they blew up your armory, and slaughtered the young men. All that is left is the women, children, and elderly. At this time, it is most important for a wise leader to pretend to be defeated, and to sell it well. Offer women. Offer food.

In the food is poison. In the women is the hatred of 1000 suns and they carry blades. They bed them, and at the agreed silent time of 1:23 am, they slit the throats of every gang member, and then in a mass gather and taking rakes, hoes, axes, and pitchforks, destroy all of the remaining guard. Then they capture the leader, put him in a kang and either offer him to the government, or behead him. If the land is that far gone they take the head and put it on a pike 500 yards down the road.

In such a situation, the stockpiling of firearms could actually empower the enemy. Whereas once a person knows how to use a blade, the world is open to him/her, and the knowledge cannot be taken away. Such roaming bands of idle men never suspect that weaker people can harbor such killing potency, so they won't come in and chop off both hands! If you have a single hand, you can do the silent killing.

The ideal situation is that you create a wide land which can be escaped, through secretive means, but only 1 way in (discounting helicopters). In such a case your firearms that are not used for hunting should be emplaced to defend that opening and a plan in place to discourage vagrants from invading, especially in force.

What kind of blades should you get? Well, a little of everything is the simple answer, but what you **must** have is:

- Adequate knives for survival, skinning game, leather and fiber cutting, fishing, etc.
- Pocket knives and leatherman type tools for handicraft
- Adequate gardening material
- Some long-range weapons such as swords and spears
- Training on all of the above¹⁰

Let's talk about firearms

When it comes to firearms, first there is the consideration of what to own and why, then of safety and storage, then of repair and restocking, cleaning and augmenting, and finally, of training (of course). The following is a bit of a stereotype, but it is a good rule:

- Rifle = hunting and target shooting
- “Assault” Rifle = urban assault, tactical, and self-defense
- Handgun = self-defense and assassination
- Shotgun = hunting and self-defense
- Machine gun = war
- Full auto = waste of ammunition
- Short barrel = self defense, and possibly illegal
- Spring loaded = usually illegal

¹⁰ Consider martial arts. Especially European and Chinese or Japanese/hybrid

No amount of blade or firearms training can totally replace hand-to-hand combat skills. However, the right weapon at the right time can and *will* confer tactical and strategic advantage to the well-trained wielder of the weapon. In terms of distance, “buying time,” potency, and the ability to deal with multiple adversaries, weapons cannot be replaced by martial arts training. A knife beats a fist, a bow a knife, a handgun a bow, and an AR-15 beats a handgun, and a 12GA tactical M1 benelli beats an AR-15, and a full automatic shotgun beats all those. But, of course, a minigun or M60 mounted on a helicopter beats that. Etc.

When you purchase your firearms, whether it is a revolver or 9mm Beretta, or a musket, you need to consider the job it needs to do. How do you know the job? Consider the problem. The **first problem** you should always consider is holes in safety and security. All holes must be plugged up and all weaknesses mitigated. If the purpose of the firearm purchase is not tourist (gift, collection, habit, etc), then it must be utilitarian. If it is utilitarian, barring a passion for something, preference, etc. then be dispassionate, calculating, and keep things very straightforward.

Example: after the Kenosha burnings in 2020, and the Portland rioting, almost every family, but especially conservatives, should have considered purchasing at minimum a tactical shotgun, and for young men aged 18-45 they should have purchased a tactical assault rifle, fully loaded. It's a \$2k-\$4k investment, but as the incident with Kyle Rittenhouse demonstrated, good handles of an AR style rifle can remove criminals and save innocent lives. With Kyle, who was unfortunately 17 years of age, he was able to eliminate 3 scumbags while retreating to a tactically safer position. If he had good training, then he could have prevented any, but if necessary taken out 10 more in defense of his position. At the rate he went, all of them would have been criminal scumbags.

In another situation a couple was able to deter burglars and would-be arsonists by simply brandishing a handgun and an AR style rifle outside their home when their gate was destroyed. However, in both situations the government (prosecutors) came down upon them. In a separate incident in New Mexico, as a man defended public property he was attacked by rioters and managed to kill one with his AR. He was released later as it was clearly self-defense. Kyle's case is more difficult because he was not over 18 and 16-18 years of age is supposed to be hunting rifles, while he carried an AR, which can be used for hunting, but probably was not his intent.

The type of firearm you need is determined not by your fears, nor preferences, nor imagination of what is wise. It is dependent on a situation which has *not yet evolved*. That makes it very difficult, unless you are on an active operation like Kyle was, or a Navy SEAL team 6 would be in capturing or killing Bin Laden, to predict what you would need. Again, the St. Louis couple had no idea that a crowd of rioters and burglars would ever break down that wrought iron gate to threaten the neighborhood. They responded with what little they had. It was sufficient to deter, but not to win. In a sustainable community in a “Mad Max” situation, this is wholly unacceptable. As nervous as the St. Louis couple was, imagine if your rich farmland is invaded by roving gangs of rapey-murderous scum, let out of prison as government run out of money to house and feed them (and don't have the political will to get rid of them permanently). In the future, it may very well be that no police exist within 60 miles to your homestead to deal with homeless vagabonds like the infamous train-riding Resendez-Ramirez. In which case, you need to consider (sometimes fantastical and ridiculous) situations which are neither pleasant to imagine, nor desirous to experience. But failure to consider future needs would be, in essence, a failure to plan or more aptly said a “plan to fail.”

Let's talk about Mil-grade weapons

Rambo 5 is not a “fun” movie, but it is satisfactory to see the cartel fall victim to an endless sequence of John Rambo laid Vietnam style tunnel traps on his remote farm in New Mexico. However, let's be realistic: if you're a Navy SEAL you don't need this document. You're not John Rambo. So why would you need mil-grade

weaponry? You almost certainly do not. You may, of course, register with the BATF and obtain a Class III license, and then go about buying expensive weaponry, which you can practice shooting on a mega-farm or at the Knob Creek Gun Shoot near Fort Knox, KY. You could even begin to purchase mortars etc. But once, again, what does that have to do with need? What does it have to do with planning? For every M60 or 20mil technical, think of all the MRE purchases you can make.

There is one weapon which seems *almost* worth the investment, but the expense of it these days is really unacceptable, unless you are very wealthy, and that is the Barret .50cal rifle. But realistically, this mil-grade weapon is for fun, or destruction, and has nothing to do with sustainability, unless you are planning to defend against tanks and armored cars! Then you'd better make sure you have armor piercing rounds.

As for Type 5 weapons: explosives, there is nothing you need that you cannot make with just basic materials if you keep certain things in stock. Consult the CIA book, Military/army manuals, or "Anarchist Cookbook" for this because we will not post a "how to" for terrorists here! However, yes is the answer as to whether or not explosives can make for effective defense of your sustainable community. However, and this is important, it can also present a direct threat to your community, its children and lives, and may invite serious federal investigations and eyes which need not be invited.

One of the reasons Rajneeshpuram lost its status as a real city was that when the cult members felt threatened they began brandishing mil-grade weapons in the original local town, and that led to the investigation by the Feds. If Osho had not fled by plane (they had their own airport), the cult members were prepared to take on the FBI and ATF (the feds) in a direct standoff, and they probably would have won a battle. Of course then the full might of the military would have squashed them, so it was better that Osho fled. But it was just stupid of the community members to brandish rifles and make grandiose and threatening statements to townspeople and government folks. All of it was instigated by a zealot, but an armed zealot (who engaged in spying on members). Bottom line is, the community stopped being a sustainable cult and became a fort and a thorn in the side of Oregon and the US government. Never challenge the lion, old or young!

Let's talk about non-firearms

The under-explored, and in our opinion, under-utilized and best area of weaponry to engage in, is not mil-grade as all sorts of would-be militias and home-grown terrorist orgs gather, thinking they can fight a government with Abrams Tanks, Apaches, and nuclear bombs - as well as the world's best specops organizations. It is non-firearm arms [bows, crossbows, blades, wrist rockets etc.] which are neither terribly regulated nor require huge .50cal sized investments. Now, a good Matthews compound bow, full-tac, will be several thousand dollars in investment, but it will not be \$4k, let alone \$10k or \$20k (as one man tried to sell me his Barret for!) You will spend \$2k - \$3k for a good setup and assortment of gear.

But you can also make a Longbow yourself, with some training, and string it, and get arrows for altogether under \$50.

There are lots of excellent homemade crossbow options, or you can buy "automatics" and spend good money on them. You **do not** need to buy professional grade target/competition crossbows and compound bows to have an effective arsenal. You can buy and train, say your 20 people, even children over 6, with a set of easily maintained recurve bows. And if people are young, spry, and grim in mood, they can eliminate a sizeable police or gang force that is on the land illegally, while falling back through a series of pits and prepared traps, to a bunker which is prepared with rifles, shotguns, and blades. Make the defense of the land a meat grinder, and even if you lose, the government lackeys or apocalyptic warlords will not think about repeating this in the future, and then you've won. It is sure if your compound or community is invaded, and you put up enough resistance, you will be completely incapable of convincing for peace, but will be pursued until utter destitution or complete death. If they want to break you, then you break them. If you cannot break them and chase them away, you can make it really, really unpalatable. But that only happens if you have the training and

the weapons, and have them placed in places where everyone knows, etc. If you have things in impossible (read: stupid) locations which are ineffective or ludicrous, well then it's the same as not having them at all.

We live, though, in the age of firearms. No amount of halberd or jousting training will enable you to defeat an invading force of assault rifle and shotgun wielding fanatics or jackboot thugs. You have to learn other survival and self-defense sciences and techniques. It's important that you plan for safety (especially firearm or explosive safety) with your sustainable community or home/family. But you need to understand that in the end, it may come down to what you know and apply, rather than what you have.

Let's talk about Home Defense

They say a home is a man's castle. Well, man or woman, the Castle Doctrine does not always apply in every state. You must know the Castle Doctrine in your state¹¹, and that includes garages and automobiles. It will determine the legality of lethality in a firefight, invasion, etc.

It's important enough to list here in a basic format from WorldPopreview. As you can see, it is not always a matter of red vs blue state, but ironically many of the states with the most strict gun laws have Castle Doctrine in place, which is very good. Whereas states like New York, Minnesota, Wisconsin, and Maryland have high crime rates and require you to retreat!

¹¹ <https://www.southuniversity.edu/news-and-blogs/2016/08/castle-doctrine-from-state-to-state-46514>
<https://www.ncsl.org/research/civil-and-criminal-justice/self-defense-and-stand-your-ground.aspx>
<https://worldpopulationreview.com/state-rankings/castle-doctrine-states>
<https://criminal.findlaw.com/criminal-law-basics/states-that-have-stand-your-ground-laws.html>

Consider, as part of your metals diversification, the purchase and stockpile of ammunition, which could be the matter of life and death in an emergency situation. Consider safe storage, ready access, and a widely diversified type of ammo for hunting, targeting, self-defense, and armor piercing, etc.

What's more, when you consider home defense, you should not only think of having a dog, or a security system, or of guns, but general placement in the home. Again, safety considered, how accessible are the weapons? Are you able to really mount an excellent defense? Do you have sensors, and other protective devices? If you live in an urban ghetto, do you have bars? If in other areas, protective film on your glass? Do you have blades in dispersed locations? Do you have lanterns and other equipment around? Do you have spare water, food, fuel, etc.? Do you have a smart home, and is it vulnerable, or is it really and truly smart? Do you have backup cutoff for your computer systems in case of intrusion that you can cut off with your phone, which is protected with 2FA? The simplest way to do this is to use a market available smart power strip and put your whole system on that strip (or however many computer systems you have).

Other things to consider about home defense are usually to do with fire, burglary, and carbon monoxide. In fact they make smart detectors for all of these, and more (such as flood). But consider also the sustainability of the home, and not only its defense. Consider, for example, the funding of the home, and is there a plan for storage of metals, for diversification of assets, emergency funds, etc.? Is the home on a sustainable power grid, and does it have backup generation? Is it in a flood plain and are there sandbags? Do you have storm shelters in place, fire extinguishers, radio in a command center, etc.? If this were still the Cold War, how would you prepare the home for a post-apocalyptic world? As it happens, China has ensured we are moving towards World War III, and in their literature and in the forums of yingpai (war-hawks) of the Chinese Communist Party, there is frequent talk and assumption of this war, and of China's "inevitable" rise to dominance. Therefore, would it not be safe to assume that one should approach the situation as if the Cold War were returned? It might not be pleasant, but after the CCP released the SARS-cov2 virus on the world, purposefully, to assassinate the economy and Trump's presidency, what isn't possible for a country that harvests living people's organs for sale to CCP elite? Be not confused about the nature of the CCP, nor feel the world is too "modern" or civilized to be such a barbarous place, with such crazy "Dr. Strangelove" futures. Prepare for the worst, hope for the best. Often the situation which evolves, opposes all of your assumptions and plans.

Survival Information

What differs from survivalism versus self-defense?

Self-defense	Short term	Usually very violent	Predator-prey	Solved by rapidly thinking
Survivalism	Long term	Violence forestalled	Master-slave	Solved by careful deliber.

As you can see, although they appear similar on the outside - because both are unwanted statuses - actually they are like yin and yang, and not similar. Therefore, it is a mistake for people to think that home defense, such as a shotgun, will be an equivalent in survival. It may work out this way, but it also may not. It may be that ammo is not the limit but water, and that in a situation people cannot go safely out of doors, nor can they get water. Let's address the issue of clean water in a minute. First, what is the most important thing in survival? It may surprise you:

1. Shelter & body-temperature
2. Fuel & fire
3. Water source
4. Security
5. Tracking & awareness
6. Food
7. Range & rescue

If it were an issue of air, of course that would come first. But as you can see, the main thing is that the list is in order of what kills you. The elements kill most survival victims, then water, wild beasts or evil men, and then food. Also many people hurt themselves doing unnecessary and risky things, often off the trail. In one case a woman split from her friend on the Appalachian trail. She was not found for 3 years, and by the time she was found (and dead), she was merely hundreds of yards from the main trail. Similarly another young man, whom they made a movie about, consumed poor food and poisoned himself, but also was mere miles away from a bridge crossing. But because of fear and isolation, and a lack of strong survival science-minded awareness, died alone, with his useless books and ideals. Third a man and his family perished in a snowstorm in the Mt. Rainer area, after getting lost, running out of fuel, and then burning everything, including the tires, while waiting. In fact, if they had the air, and would make the water from snow, by remaining huddled together in the care, underneath the best clothes they could find, they would have (barely) survived. The father was most to blame, as he planned, or failed to plan, the outing.

Survival situations evolve out of the natural chaos of the Universe. In the beginning such situations do not usually, with the exception of heists, hijackings and kidnappings, appear violent and sudden. Rather they take people by surprise later. A group of hikers atop Half Dome, taken by surprise by a lightning storm, and rushing down get injured or encounter a forest fire, etc.

When it comes to sustainable, resilient homes, businesses, and communities, please bear in mind most people will **not** ever encounter a shark attack or a roaming band of swarthy pirates or a highwayman. But, as you never know, it is important to consider the possibilities. Cartels, and of course police, have been known to bust into unprepared homes with automatic weapons pointed and even firing! Recently, in 2020, a man was reported (unlawfully by a neighbor) as being in a domestic dispute. He was not, the neighbor simply wanted quiet. The police showed up and surprised him. He came to the door with a weapon, and before he could set it don, was shot, dead. Nevermind that he was prepared and within his rights. He died due to negligence. But while it appears a self-defense situation, actually it was a survival issue. Neighbors rarely victimize strangers in such a way the first time. The entire situation may have been avoided, if the two were better neighbors. As it is,

by ignoring animus, the neighbor got his dark revenge, and through the reasonable ignorance of his victim. These situations are rare, but not rare enough. So one should consider the long term ramifications of various policies and behaviors of one's house, business, etc.

An aggressive, hostile offense seems like good defense to insecure people. But actually it can invite danger, and imitate the opposite, which is a meek, prey-like demeanor. Both invite tigers and wolves. But while the sheep can buy a gun to slay a wolf, a haughty buck who proudly displays his weapons might invite a cunning tiger to try out his claws and stripes. The stripes, in essence, are more frightening than the claws and fangs!

The following list is a non-exhaustive of items to consider in stocking the home or business for long range survival:

- Canned goods & MRE
- Toolkits
- Healing kits / first aid
- Fuel
 - Butane
 - Propane
 - Gasoline
 - Oils
 - Batteries, etc.
 - Wood
- Thread and needle
- Packaged goods, conveniences
- Maps and escape plans
- Seeds (at least 3 years of edible vegetables)
- Maps to wild food sources, if known
- Barter lists, suppliers etc.
-

Let's talk about learning Survivalism

Considering you almost certainly have no real skills, our best advice is to read Peterson Field Guides, Tom Brown books, and practice learning skills, such as starting fire, over time. It is not necessary to be capable of flint knapping, or making a crossbow, etc. But, realistically, you mostly need a resiliency network of people, and you can list their skills (or lack of), and the vulnerabilities of the network, as well as its strengths. Distance and age are automatic disabilities. Gender is a disability depending on the mentality of the women, although men are increasingly more effeminized and many young people in adult ages have almost no clue about natural roughness, male or female. Realistically, a useless male though is typically some kind of positive, while women and children are a disability, all other things, and especially attitudes being equal.

However, women can drastically increase their survivability and positive use through a drastic attitude shift. In season 2 of Bear Grylls' Island, the women performed so poorly that for season 3, the producers screened women to find more aware and survival oriented women, and they were able to compete better - in mixed teams - the 3rd season. But in season 2 some women were in serious danger, without help from the producers, many would have died of dehydration. While men do argue and display egotistic bravado, they all get down to business fairly soon, and civilize quickly. In one episode of Survivor, the men won a chicken, but via whining and using female charms, the women conned the men into giving them the chicken, out of feeling

sorry for them. That may be a human survival technique, but in raw nature, away from cameras, it simply is a hindrance to survival. The rules of Survival are pretty strict, and while not genderless, they are equitable.

Clothing and Apparel related Survival

It's important to acquire the following items to secure your survival in urban or rural environs:

- Spare blankets
- Extra coats
- Hats, gloves, etc.
 - Leather
 - Cold weather
 - Tactical/shooting/hunting
 - Rubber or latex-like gloves
- Balaclavas for family members (or ski masks)
- Spare thread, yarn, needles, etc. (to make quilts and repair clothes)
- Buttons
- Jeans
- Cover-alls
- "Long johns" or other warm under-wear
- Optional: wet wear such as a wet suit or diving related equipment
- Extra socks and under clothes
- Shoes
- Water proof boots
- Rubber boots or even entire rubber waders such as fishermen wear
- Ghilli Suit and camo/fatigues
- Zip ties or handcuffs
- Batons, survival knives, leathermans, etc.
- Tactical vests
- Armor carriers (AR500 is the most comfortable available)
- Armor (NIJ level 3 or above)... try to make it lightweight
- Optional: pads
- Optional: devtac or other ballistic helmets.
- Gas masks and N95 style masks
-

It's important to remember that the purpose is purely to be prepared. Store things in cool, dry places, and hopefully you never have to buy them again!

Canning and Food Prep, etc.

In the learning of canning, jarring, and making your own food, we are no experts. What we provide here is a small part of what you need to know, so please consider joining groups and learning more. Also, as mentioned before you can buy MREs and other dried/vacuumed goods to shore up your own supplies.